

Studies of the Action of *p*-Chloroacetophenone on Different Unsymmetrical Diaryl Thioureas in Presence of Bromine

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p-Chloroacetophenone has been made to undergo cyclocondensation with seven different unsymmetrical diaryl thioureas in presence of bromine and the resulting 4-thiazolines have been hydrolysed to ascertain their structure. A possible mechanism has been suggested regarding the orientation of the substituents in the thiazoline nucleus.

MANY authors have studied the action of Sym. diaryl thioureas with α -haloketones¹ or with ketones in presence of halogens like iodine² or bromine³ or with α -haloacids and have reported the formation of 4-thiazolines and 4-thiazolidones respectively. But few authors have worked with unsymmetrical diaryl thioureas. Some authors have reported the formation of isomeric mixtures of 4-thiazolines by the action of unsymmetrical diaryl thioureas with α -haloketones⁴ or with ethylene dibromide⁵ and the formation of isomeric mixtures of 4-thiazolidones by the action of unsymmetrical diaryl thioureas with α -haloacids⁷.

By analogy with the action of α -haloketones on Sym. dialkyl (aryl) thioureas and the action of thiourea and phenyl thiourea on ketones and iodine or bromine the following possibility of the reaction between the unsymmetrical diaryl thiourea and ketone in presence of bromine, resulting in the formation of two isomeric mixtures of 4-thiazoline (IV, V) may be suggested.

That there seems to be a selective action depending upon the amount of tautomeric forms of the thiourea (II, III) present in the reaction mixture with the resultant formation of only one isomer of the 4-thiazoline (IV, V) has been suspected and worth investigation.

With a view to studying the influence of electron displacement effects of the substituents on the preferential formation of one isomer of the 4-thiazoline (IV or V) seven unsymmetrical diaryl thioureas of

the type R-NHC(S)NH-R' namely, N-phenyl-N'-*p*-nitrophenyl-thiourea, N-*p*-bromophenyl-N'-*p*-nitrophenyl-thiourea, N-phenyl-N'-*p*-bromophenyl-thiourea, N-phenyl-N'-(4-phenyl-2-thiazolyl)-thiourea, N-phenyl-N'-*p*-carboxyphenyl-thiourea, N-*p*-bromophenyl-N'-*p*-carboxyphenyl-thiourea, N-*p*-iodophenyl-N'-*p*-carboxyphenylthiourea have been selected and made to undergo cyclocondensation separately with *p*-chloroacetophenone in presence of bromine. In selecting the unsymmetrical diaryl thioureas it has always been tried to put an electron withdrawing substituent on one phenyl ring and an electron releasing substituent on the other phenyl ring or any one of the two (electron withdrawing or releasing substituent) on any one phenyl ring, so that the tautomerisation of the thiourea may be shifted to either II or III (more or less exclusively). The final products have been studied on TLC with Silica Gel as adsorbent in ten solvent systems (Benzene-dioxan (90 : 10), Benzene-chloroform (90 : 10), Ethyl acetate-acetic acid (60 : 40), Benzene-methanol (70 : 30), Benzene-ethyl acetate-acetic acid (80 : 10 : 10), Chloroform-acetone-ammonia (0.89) (30 : 30 : 0.5), Chloroform-ethyl acetate-ammonia (33 : 30 : 0.5), Chloroform-methanol-acetic acid (20 : 12 : 2), *n*-Butanol-water-ammonia (27 : 3 : 1.5), Benzene-iso-propanol (30 : 30) to ascertain the number of isomers formed. The final products were purified by column chromatography using benzene, benzene-methanol, benzene-ethyl acetate mixtures as eluents and silica gel for column chromatography as the absorbent and hydrolysed⁸ by ethanolic HCl to ascertain the position of the substituents. The m.p., I.R. absorption peaks of the oxo compounds (hydrolysed products) were compared with the m.p. and I.R. data of the oxo compounds prepared by unambiguous method (i.e., by the action of *p*-chloroacetophenone on appropriate Sym. diaryl thiourea in presence of iodine and subsequent hydrolysis of the 4-thiazoline) and I.R. data of the 4-thiazolines from which the hydrolysed products were obtained.

Experimental

1. Preparation of 2-*p*-bromophenylimino-3-*p*-nitrophenyl-4-*p*-chlorophenyl-4-thiazoline:—The title

compound was prepared from *p*-chloroacetophenone (1.6 g) and *N*-*p*-bromophenyl-*N'*-*p*-nitrophenylthiourea (4 g) in presence of bromine (1.6 g) by the method of Dash and Mahapatra⁸. The compound was crystallised from glacial acetic acid and further purified by running through column of Silica Gel. Yield-75%, m.p.-211°.

(Found S, 6.41, C₂₁H₁₃N₃SO₂BrCl, requires S, 6.57%)

The other thiazolines were prepared by the same method; their yields, melting points and analytical data have been recorded in Table 1.

2. *Hydrolysis of 2-p-bromophenylimino-3-p-nitrophenyl-4-p-chlorophenyl-4-thiazoline*: The title compound was hydrolysed by the method of Bhargava and Kaul⁹. It was crystallised from alcohol and further purified by column chromatography. Yield 80%, m.p.-180°.

Found S, 9.56, C₁₅H₉O₃N₂SOCl requires S, 9.62%.

The other thiazolines were hydrolysed by the same method; their yields, melting points and analytical data have been recorded in Table 1.

with the hydrolysed product of 2-*p*-nitrophenylimino-3-*p*-nitrophenyl-4-*p*-chlorophenyl-4-thiazoline. Their I.R. curves are also identical and the retention of the strong absorption at 1515 cm⁻¹ and 1345 cm⁻¹ (characteristic peaks for conjugated nitro group) in the I.R. curve of the hydrolysed product clearly indicates that the *p*-nitrophenyl ring is attached to the position 3 of the thiazoline nucleus. The identity of the hydrolysed products under sl. nos. 5, 6 and 7 with the hydrolysed product of 2-*p*-carboxyphenylimino-3-*p*-carboxyphenyl-4-*p*-chlorophenyl-4-thiazoline is established from the m.p., mixed m.p. and I.R. curves. Again the retention of strong absorption peaks at 1700 cm⁻¹ and 1680 cm⁻¹ in the I.R. curves of the hydrolysed products indicates that the prepared 4-thiazoline compounds under sl nos. 5, 6 and 7 have *p*-carboxyphenyl ring in the position 3.

The m.p. and I.R. curve of the hydrolysed product of compound no. 3 is identical with the hydrolysed product of 2-phenylimino-3-phenyl-4-*p*-chlorophenyl-4-thiazoline and shows no depression in mixed m.p. and hence the unsubstituted phenyl ring is attached to position 3 of the thiazoline nucleus. The hydrolysed product of compound no. 4 is different from the hydrolysed product of 2-phenylimino-3-phenyl-4-*p*-chlorophenyl-4-thiazoline

TABLE-1

Compound No.	Before hydrolysis				After hydrolysis						
	R	R'	% of yield	M.P. in °C	% of Sulphur Found Calc.		R'	% of yield	M.P. in °C	% of Sulphur Found Calc.	
1.	C ₆ H ₅ -	<i>p</i> -C ₆ H ₄ NO ₂ -	72	222	7.50	7.85	<i>p</i> -C ₆ H ₄ NO ₂ -	96	179	9.42	9.62
2.	<i>p</i> -C ₆ H ₄ Br-	<i>p</i> -C ₆ H ₄ NO ₂ -	75	211	6.41	6.57	<i>p</i> -C ₆ H ₄ NO ₂ -	80	180	9.50	9.62
*3.	<i>p</i> -C ₆ H ₄ Br-	C ₆ H ₅ -	81	220	7.30	7.24	C ₆ H ₅ -	98	160	18.85	11.11
4.	C ₆ H ₅ -	4-phenyl-2-thiazolyl-	57	247	14.70	14.37	4-phenyl-2-thiazolyl-	94	240	17.11	17.27
5.	<i>p</i> -C ₆ H ₄ Br-	<i>p</i> -C ₆ H ₄ CO ₂ H-	52	250	6.60	6.66	<i>p</i> -C ₆ H ₄ CO ₂ H-	92	206	9.45	9.65
6.	<i>p</i> -C ₆ H ₄ I-	<i>p</i> -C ₆ H ₄ CO ₂ H-	48	291	5.87	6.00	<i>p</i> -C ₆ H ₄ CO ₂ H-	87	205	9.48	9.65
7.	C ₆ H ₅ -	<i>p</i> -C ₆ H ₄ CO ₂ H-	51	295	7.20	7.90	<i>p</i> -C ₆ H ₄ CO ₂ H-	74	205.5	9.56	9.65

* This compound gave two spots in the T. L. C studies, indicating the contamination of the other isomer which was separated by column chromatography.

Results and Discussion

TLC studies have definitely proved that all the final products (4-thiazolines) are pure compounds and not mixture of isomers except only in one case, i.e., compound under sl no. 3 of Table 1 which however has been separated successfully by column chromatography. The presence of substituted arylimino group at position 2 has been proved by hydrolysis experiment which led to the formation of oxo compounds having characteristic strong absorption peaks at around 1650 cm⁻¹ and 1620 cm⁻¹ (in some cases at 1615 cm⁻¹, 1630 cm⁻¹). The hydrolysed products under sl nos. 1 and 2 are identical as is evidenced by the m.p. mixed m.p., and is also identical

and hence it can be safely concluded that the 4-phenyl-2-thiazolyl group is attached to position 3 of the thiazoline prepared.

Thus on the basis of the products obtained, it is the phenyl ring with strong electron attracting group goes to the ring nitrogen (position 3) and the phenyl ring containing electron releasing substituents in comparison to that present in position 3, goes to the imino nitrogen at position 2. The results are in good agreement with the observation of Singh⁷ and Pandey⁹ on the action of unsymmetrical diaryl thioureas on monochloro acetic acid and also with Dains et al¹⁰ who worked with unsymmetrical thiourea and ethylene dibromide.

Thus by proper selection of the symmetrical diaryl thioureas it has been possible to direct the course of reaction in such a way that the desired single isomer could be prepared. The explanation for the formation of single isomer may be suggested as follows.

Mechanism

The addition of bromine to the ketone in presence of sunlight forms α -bromoketone and HBr.

The HBr thus formed, partly escapes and partly remains in the solution making it acidic.

The unsymmetrical diaryl thiourea remains in the resonating form.

The proton from HBr adds on to the resonating structure (VIIa) and forms carbonium ion (VIII).

Now the carbonium ion (VIII) resonates, forming a double bond with the nitrogen atom using its lone pair and eliminating a proton, yielding either IXa and/or IXb.

The formation of IXa or IXb depends on the easy availability of the lone pair of nitrogen atom which is again dependant on the nature of the substituent, i.e., R and R' of the thiourea.

The electron shifting in the stage VIII of the N-phenyl-N'-p-nitrophenyl-thiourea will be as follows.

The strong electron withdrawing effect of the nitro group on the phenyl nucleus at para position

shifts the lone pair of the nitrogen atom of the thiourea to its side, developing a partial double bond, hence a positive charge on the nitrogen atom. This VIIIa is energetically unstable. Hence the carbonium ion in this case resonates by interacting with the lone pair on the other nitrogen atom and forms IXb.

This form of the thiourea led to the formation of 2-phenyl-imino-3-p-nitrophenyl-4-p-chlorophenyl-4-thiazoline (no. 1 in Table 1) by the cyclocondensation with p-chloroacetophenone in presence of bromine.

Similar is the case with N-phenyl-N'-p-carboxyphenyl-thiourea; IX b which led to the formation of 2-phenylimino-3-p-carboxyphenyl-4-p-chlorophenyl-4-thiazoline (no. 7).

The cases with N-p-bromophenyl-N'-p-nitrophenyl thiourea, N-p-bromophenyl-N'-p-carboxyphenyl-thiourea and N-p-iodophenyl-N'-p-carboxyphenyl-thiourea are more clear, because the nitro group as well as the carboxy group are strong electron withdrawing groups and the lone pair on the nitrogen in this side is highly disturbed. On the other hand, bromine and iodine on benzene nucleus, although slightly electron withdrawing (-I effect) have overall electron releasing effect (+M effect). Thus the lone pair on nitrogen in this side is not disturbed and free for interaction with the carbonium ion.

Thus the thioureas gave 2-p-bromophenylimino-3-p-nitrophenyl-4-p-chlorophenyl-4-thiazoline, (no. 2), 2-p-bromophenylimino-3-p-carboxyphenyl-4-p-chlorophenyl-4-thiazoline (no. 5), 2-p-iodophenylimino-3-p-carboxyphenyl-4-p-chlorophenyl-4-thiazoline (no. 6) respectively as shown in Table 1.

Thiazole is a pi excessive *s*-heteroaromatic. An electron density diagram¹¹ of thiazole shows a large negative charge on 5, a positive charge of roughly one-third that amount on 2, whereas the position 4 is neutral. As a result of the electron deficiency of the position 2 of the thiazole nucleus (to which nitrogen atom of the thiourea is attached), the lone pair of the nitrogen of N-phenyl-N'-(4-phenyl-2-thiazolyl)-thiourea is highly disturbed and attracted towards the thiazole nucleus and favours the carbonium ion resonance in the opposite direction.

This led to the formation of 2-phenylimino-3-(4-phenyl-2-thiazolyl)-4-*p*-chlorophenyl-4-thiazoline (no. 4).

In N-phenyl-N'-*p*-bromophenyl-thiourea the bromine atom at para position of the phenyl nucleus has both electron pulling (-I effect) and electron releasing effect (+M effect). The net pushing effect is too weak to give a clear picture in advance, so both IXa and IXb will be present in the system, although the IXb will be in slight excess, and hence

two isomeric thiazolines, i.e., 2-*p*-bromophenylimino-3-phenyl-4-*p*-chlorophenyl-4-thiazoline and 2-phenylimino-3-*p*-bromophenyl-4-*p*-chlorophenyl-4-thiazoline have been obtained and the former isomer was the major product.

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References

1. S. P. KHARIDIA and J. J. TRIVEDI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1965, **42**(9), 647.
2. B. C. DASH and G. N. MAHAPATRA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1967, **44**(11), 939.
3. B. C. DASH and G. N. MAHAPATRA, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1967, **5**(1), 40.
4. R. P. RAO, *Curr. Sci.*, 1966, **35**(21), 541.
5. J. BARTOSEWSKI and Z. JERMANOWSKA, *Rocz. Chem.*, 1963, **37**, 11.
6. L. DASHEN and R. Q. BREWSTER, *Trans. Kansas. Acad. Sci.*, 1937, **40**, 103.
7. (i) S. R. SINGH, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1975 **52**(8), 734 ;
(ii) R. P. RAO, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1971, **48**, 253.
8. P. N. BHARGAVA and C. KAUL, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1955, **32**(1), 50.
9. H. N. PANDY et al. *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1972, **49**(1), 181.
10. F. B. DAINS et al., *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1921, **43**, 613 ; 1925, **47**, 1981.
11. A. PULLMAN and METZGER, *Bull. Soc. Chim. France*, 1948, **15**, 1021.